

Salical-N-*o*-aminobenzenesulphonyl Glycine and its Metal Chelates

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Salical-N-*o*-aminobenzenesulphonyl glycine (RH₃), a Schiff base has been prepared by condensing *o*-aminobenzenesulphonyl glycine and salicylaldehyde, which forms water soluble complexes with Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) having the general formula M(RH), xH₂O. Data on magnetic properties, electronic spectra in aqueous solutions and ir spectra in KBr matrices are recorded and a discussion has been made.

A Schiff base, salical-N-*o*-aminobenzenesulphonyl glycine (RH₃) has been prepared by condensing *o*-aminobenzenesulphonyl glycine¹ with salicylaldehyde and a study on its donor properties has been made. The Schiff base forms water soluble complexes with Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) of the general type M(RH), xH₂O where x=0 for Cu(II) complex and 2 for the

were dried in air and analysed. The compound is sparingly soluble in water, soluble in ether, highly soluble in ethanol and methanol, insoluble in benzene and petroleum ether, m.p. 176°. [Found : C, 54.03 ; H, 4.24 ; N, 8.54 per cent. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₄O₅N₂S : C, 53.91 ; H, 4.19 ; N, 8.39 per cent].

FIG. 1

corresponding complexes of Ni(II) and Co(II). The four coordination sites of the ligand RH₃ are shown in Fig. 1. A preliminary notice has been published².

Experimental

Preparation of the Schiff base (RH₃)

o-Aminobenzenesulphonyl glycine (0.5 g.) was mixed with 2 ml. salicylaldehyde and the mixture was heated for half an hour on steambath. To the clear yellow liquid obtained was now added 30 ml. of dry benzene. Water and excess of salicylaldehyde were removed by azeotropic distillation of benzene. Golden yellow shining crystals were obtained. They

Preparation of metal chelates

A. Copper(II)

(i) *Bis* (Salicylaldehyde) copper (II) was dissolved in boiling chloroform and to the solution was added the solution of *o*-aminobenzenesulphonyl glycine in methanol. The mixture was warmed on a steambath. A green compound separated. It was filtered, washed with methanol and finally with benzene. The product was dried in a vacuum desiccator over H₂SO₄. The compound was soluble in ethanol and water and less so in methanol. [Found : Cu, 15.92 ; N, 7.00 per cent. Calcd. for Cu(RH) : Cu, 16.08 ; N, 7.08 per cent].

(ii) The compound (RH₃) was suspended in water and freshly precipitated alkali-free CuO was added to it. The mixture was heated on a steam bath for sometime and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness in vacuum. The residue was washed well with acetone, filtered and dried in a vacuum desiccator over H₂SO₄. [Found : Cu, 15.90 ; N, 6.95 per cent].

B. Nickel(II)

Bis(Salicylaldehyde) nickel (II) (0.01 mole) was dissolved in methanol by refluxing. To the solution was added a methanolic solution of *o*-aminobenzenesulphonyl glycine.

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sulphonyl glycine (0.01 mole). The mixture was refluxed for an hour, when yellowish green crystals appeared. The product was filtered, washed first with methanol and then with dry benzene. It was dried in vacuum over H_2SO_4 . [Found : Ni, 13.78 ; N, 6.47 per cent. Calcd. for Ni (RH), $2H_2O$: Ni, 13.76 ; N, 6.56 per cent].

On dehydration at 110° it lost water with a change in colour from yellowish green to snuff-like. The loss in weight corresponded to two molecules of H_2O . (Loss found : 8.66 per cent. Calcd. : 8.44 per cent). The anhydrous compound was analysed for Ni. [Found : 14.74 per cent. Calcd. : 15.02 per cent].

C. Cobalt (II)

Orange yellow cobalt compound was obtained following similar procedure as in the case of Ni (II) complex. [Found : Co., 14.01 ; N, 6.41 per cent. Calcd. for Co (RH), $2H_2O$: Co, 13.80 ; N, 6.56 per cent].

On dehydration at 110° it lost weight and the loss corresponded to two molecules of H_2O . [Loss found : 8.57 per cent. Calcd. : 8.43 per cent]. The anhydrous compound was analysed for Co. [Found : 14.91 per cent. Calcd. : 15.07 per cent].

These complexes were found to be weakly acidic. The conductance data in aqueous solution also supported their weakly acidic characteristic. The pK_a values were determined by potentiometric titration at a constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.5$) using KNO_3 as the neutral salt at 30° and evaluated following Bjerrum's *half- \bar{n}* -method. The results are stated in Table 1. Taking the enhancement of the acidity to be a function of the metal-nitrogen bond strength i.e. proportional to the stability of the metal chelates³, the stability may be stated to be in the order $Cu(II) > Co(II) > Ni(II)$.

The magnetic susceptibilities by Gouy method and electronic spectra employing Hilger's UVISPEK spectrophotometer, were measured at room temperature and the results along with other properties are stated in Table 1.

TABLE I—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA, MAGNETIC DATA AND SOME OTHER DATA

Compound	Colour	pK_a values	μ_{eff} (BM)	Temperature ($^\circ K$)	aq max (nm)	$\log \epsilon$
RH ₃	Golden yellow	—	—	—	308	2.61
					242.5	3.99
					205	4.45
Cu(RH)	Green glistening	6.10	2.18	303	645-50	1.93
					390	3.53
					295	3.89
					230	4.16
					212	4.20
Co (RH), $2H_2O$	Orange yellow	7.90	4.93	304	670	0.35
					550	1.08
					375	2.73
					305	3.44
					240	3.75
Co(RH)	Orange	—	5.09	304	—	—
Ni(RH), $2H_2O$	Yellowish green glistening	8.80	3.11	303	665	1.15
					395	3.51
					295	3.79
					240	4.17
Ni(RH)	Snuff-like	—	3.13	303	—	—

TABLE 2—SOME IMPORTANT IR BANDS (CM⁻¹) OF THE LIGAND AND ITS COMPLEXES WITH THEIR PROVISIONAL ASSIGNMENTS

RH ₃	Cu(RH)	Ni(RH)	Co(RH)	Ni(RH), 2H ₂ O	Assignments
—	—	3440-3280(s b)	3450-3290(s b)	3450-3185(s b)	H-bonded N-H and/or O-H stretches
3400(m sp)	3460(s b)	—	—	—	N-H stretches
3220(s sp)	—	—	—	—	H-bonded O-H stretch
2470(w b)	—	—	—	—	-COOH O-H stretch
1730(s sp)	—	—	—	—	due to -COOH group
1620(s sp)	1630(s sp)	1640(s sp)	1638(s sp)	1630(s sp)	-C=N-stretches
—	1592(s sp)	1610(s sp)	1615(s sp)	1620(s sh)	-CO ₂ ⁻ antisymmetrical stretch
—	—	—	—	1595(s b)	due to lattice or coordinated water
—	1390(s sp)	1396(s sp)	1395(s sp)	1385(s sp)	-CO ₂ ⁻ symmetrical stretches
1370(w sp)	—	—	—	1338(s b)	due to OH bending
1330(s sp)	1320(s b)	1313(s sp)	1320(s sp)	1306(s sp)	due to -SO ₂ N< group (Band II)
1168(s sp)	1155(s sp)	1158(s sp)	1161(s sp)	1164(s sp)	due to -SO ₂ N< group (Band I)
—	570(m b)	585(s b)	580(m b)	580(s b)	M-N stretches
—	552(m b)	542(s b)	542(m b)	540(s b)	M-O stretches

s—strong ; m—medium ; w—weak ; sp—sharp ; b—broad ; sh—shoulder.

The ir spectra of the ligand and its complexes were recorded in KBr matrices. Some ir bands of interest with their provisional assignments^{4,5,6} are stated in Table 2.

Discussion

The Schiff base obtained by condensing *o*-aminobenzenesulphonyl glycine with salicylaldehyde, may act as a tetradentate ligand. The possible bonding sites on complex formation are shown in Fig. 1. The magnetochemical studies indicate that the chelates M(RH) may have distorted octahedral structures evidently by intermolecular interactions—supported by ir spectral data.

Magnetic data^{7, 8} are often useful tool for characterisation of many complex compounds. The magnetic moment values of Cu(II) complexes are generally ranging from 1.8 to 2.2 BM^{7, 9} having distorted octahedral stereochemistry. However a few compounds

are known of approximately tetrahedral stereochemistry. In the present case the observed value (2.18 BM) is in the said region. Octahedral Ni(II) should have magnetic moments ranging from 2.9 to 3.4 BM depending on the magnitude of orbital contribution and tetrahedral Ni(II) complexes have moments 3.5 to 4.2 BM⁷. In the present cases, the Ni(II) complexes are found to have magnetic moments 3.11 and 3.13 BM, suggests octahedral structures. In Co(II) complexes, the observed magnetic moments are 4.93 and 5.09 BM—values expected for high spin octahedral complexes^{7, 9}.

Electronic spectra of Cu(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes in aqueous solution support octahedral stereochemistry. Regarding Cu(II) complex the broad peak observed at 645-650 nm is due to d-d transitions and the maximum at 390 nm is charge transfer band^{10, 11}. For Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes in aqueous solution, the absorption maxima actually observed and the corresponding ϵ_{\max} values support

octahedral structures for the complexes¹¹. The Co(II) complex has exhibited two d-d bands at 670 and 550 nm due to the transitions from ${}^4T_{1g}$ ground state to ${}^4A_{2g}$ (F) and ${}^4T_{1g}$ (P) states respectively and one charge transfer band at 375 nm. Regarding Ni(II) complex, the absorption bands at 665 and 395 nm are in accordance with the expected transitions from ${}^3A_{2g}$ state to ${}^3T_{1g}$ (F) and ${}^3T_{1g}$ (P) states respectively¹². Electronic spectra of the ligand in aqueous solution show a number of peaks in the uv

octahedral structure may be conferred on it and by analogy on Co(RH), $2H_2O$ as well.

The separation (Δ) between antisymmetrical and symmetrical COO^- stretches for the complexes against that for free carboxylate ion has been shown to be dependable upon metal oxygen bonding type^{14, 15}. The increase of separation in comparison to free carboxylate anion (A), gives rise to asymmetrical structure (B), and decrease or no change to symmetri-

region. In the case of metal chelates, peaks in the uv region are also observed, which are closely comparable to that of the ligand itself.

Important ir bands of the ligand (RH_3) and its metal chelates are shown in Table 2. The ligand possesses a number of bonding sites. From a comparative study of the ir spectra of the ligand and its complexes one may draw out the possible bonding sites of the ligand.

The disappearance of the ligand band at 3220 cm^{-1} due to partially associated OH group, on complex formation, could not be definitely detected due to overlapping of N-H stretch. However, the ligand bands at 1730 cm^{-1} due to $-COOH$ group and at 1370 cm^{-1} due to OH bending has disappeared in the complexes. Therefore $-OH$ and $-COOH$ groups are definitely involved in the bond formation through oxygen atoms with the metal ions. The ligand band at 1620 cm^{-1} due to $-C=N-$ stretch¹³ shifted to higher frequencies, and at 1330 cm^{-1} due to $-SO_2N<$ group to lower frequencies in all the complexes, indicate that these two nitrogen atoms are also involved in bond formation. The bonding of oxygen and nitrogen atoms to metal ions has been further confirmed by observed M-O and M-N stretches as shown in Table 2. Thus the ligand (RH_3) may act as a tetradentate one, which has been shown in Fig. 1.

In the compound Ni (RH), $2H_2O$ the bands at 1595 cm^{-1} may be regarded as evidences for the water molecules coordinated^{6,14}. So a distorted

octahedral structure (C). The antisymmetrical and symmetrical COO^- stretches of the complexes along with their separation are shown in Table 3. The values of N-*p*-toluenesulphonyl glycinate anion (R_tH^-)¹⁶ and N-benzenesulphonyl glycinate anion (R_bH^-)¹⁷, which are taken as the standards, have also been included in Table 3. From the data it is evident that the structure (C) may be conferrable on the M(RH)

TABLE 3—SEPARATION OF $-CO_2^-$ STRETCHES (CM^{-1})

Compound	Antisymmetrical	Symmetrical	Separation (Δ)
K(R_tH)	1625	1394	231
K(R_bH)	1618	1402	216
Cu(RH)	1592	1390	202
Ni(RH)	1610	1396	214
Co(RH)	1615	1395	220
Ni(RH), $2H_2O$	1620	1385	235

chelates. So there is intermolecular interaction between second oxygen atom of $-CO_2^-$ group and metal atom of the second molecule. Thus for distorted octahedral structure of M(RH), another interaction may take place through one oxygen atom of sulphonyl group. The shift of ir stretch (band I) of $-SO_2N<$ group of the ligand to lower frequencies

in the complexes, may be regarded as evidences of such interaction¹⁸. But in the present cases the shifts are not so appreciable, therefore it may be suggested that there exist weak intermolecular interactions. Among the chelates Cu(RH), Co(RH) and Ni(RH), it is evident from the data that such interactions in Cu(RH) are slightly stronger. This is also supported by the fact that diaquocompounds Co(RH), 2H₂O and Ni(RH), 2H₂O have been isolated, but the corresponding Cu(II) compound could not be prepared under identical conditions.

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